

Hybrid autophage propulsion for space launch vehicles: a promising concept

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Abstract

In this article, hybrid autophage propulsion for space launch vehicles is being investigated. This novel architecture uses the launcher's propellant as structure, removing the need for tanks and staging altogether. The resulting single-stage-to-orbit vehicle offers improvements in design complexity, production costs and logistics. Smaller launch vehicles can be designed as a result of the reduced dry mass. In the current context of rapid growth in the number of small satellites, maturing this technology could lead to more affordable and resource-efficient launchers.

In 2008, Yemets *et al.* began ground-testing a solid autophage engine. This technology was made possible by the excellent mechanical properties and combustion performance of modern thermoplastics, allowing their use as both rocket fuel and structure. This paper presents the first autophage concept relying on hybrid propulsion. During the flight, both solid fuel and liquid oxidizer are inserted into the engine to produce thrust. The vehicle shortens until only the rocket engine and the payload remains. The specifics of the autophage architecture are described: during steady combustion, the solid fuel is continuously replaced as it burns, making the chamber geometry constant and solving the O/F-shift problem. The O/F ratio now becomes a geometrical parameter, with small variations. A performance model is built to optimize the main design parameters. Preliminary results for the vehicles to be developed by Alpha Impulsion are presented and compared to a competing commercial launch vehicle.

To develop autophage launch vehicles with optimal performance, several challenges are identified: the mechanical properties of the plastic structure, the balance between fuel insertion and regression, the impact of variable launcher length on structural dynamics, and other challenges relevant to all single-stage launchers.

Nomenclature

Acronyms

ABS	Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene
AN, AP	Ammonium nitrate, -perchlorate
HTP	High-Test Peroxide (H_2O_2)
HTPB	Hydroxyl-terminated polybutadiene
LOx	Liquid Oxygen
O/F	Oxidizer/Fuel Mass ratio
PE	Polyethylene (LDPE, HDPE, UHMWPE)
SSTO	Single stage to orbit

Symbols

\dot{f}	Time evolution of the aspect ratio = v_a/D
\dot{r}	Fuel regression rate
C^*	Characteristic velocity
C_F	Nozzle Thrust coefficient
E	Elastic Modulus
f	aspect ratio L/D of launcher or structure
I	Second moment of area
I_v	Specific impulse per unit volume $\rho_m I_{sp}$
I_{sp}, I_{vac}	Specific impulse (in vacuum)
M	Mass or Mach
r/t	radius to thickness ratio of a hollow cylinder

TWR Thrust-to-Weight Ratio

v_a Autophage velocity (same as insertion velocity)

Greek symbols

α	Custom stiffness parameter
ε	Nozzle expansion ratio
η	efficiency
γ	Adiabatic coefficient
μ	Coefficient of dry friction
ρ	density

Subscripts

ch	chamber
e	External (diameter), Engine
f	Final, Flame (temperature)
i	Initial (mass), Inner (diameter)
ins	insertion
m	mean, average
p	propellants
s	Specific (power), Screw
u	upper

1. Introduction and state of the art

Autophage propulsion, in contrast to the conventional concept of rocket staging, involves the continuous reduction of the rocket's dry mass throughout its flight. Typically, this is achieved by incorporating designs that allow the insertion of the rocket's main body (propellants) into the rocket engine, as can be seen in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. General conceptual autophage architecture.

It results in a vehicle that steadily diminishes in length until the engine has joined the fairing and propulsion stops. In 1936, L. Damblanc [1] introduced a rocket composed of numerous micro-stages with heat-fusible joints to approach this idea. In 1958, L.W. Mullane [2] invented the use of a solid grain as the rocket's main structural element, and several ideas to force it into a combustion chamber. In 1960, Z.A. Typaldos [3] proposed the first single-stage rocket explicitly termed "autophage," with the solid grain and heat-fusible metal structure being passively inserted into the chamber solely by the action of the engine's thrust. In 1987, Corbett and Belisle [4] invented various architectures to actively insert the grain. No prototype had been tested up to this point. Research efforts on autophage propulsion were revitalized in the 2000s through the work of V. Yemets *et al.* in Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (Ukraine) and University of Glasgow (UK) ([5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11]). To the authors' knowledge, these publications are presently the only experimental literature on autophage launchers. This research continues

within the Ukrainian company Promin Aerospace [12]. This autophage engine employs two unmixed solid propellants, one of which is a thermoplastic tube intended to serve as the launcher's structure. A new component known as a "vaporizer" is used to vaporize the propellants on a hot metallic wall using chamber heat conducted through the wall. The resulting gases are then injected into the combustion chamber, sustaining the cycle.

In this context, the present article proposes a new approach by the angle of hybrid propulsion. Hybrid propulsion offers certain advantages over solid and liquid propellant rockets, including simplicity, safety, low cost, reliability, throttleability and performance. The historical drawbacks of hybrids, such as low regression rates and combustion efficiency, have been partially addressed through increasingly well-known technical solutions: swirling injection [13, 14], grain surface generating turbulence, such as helical grains [15], and highly energetic, fast-regressing fuels [16]. Thermoplastic materials play a significant role in hybrid propulsion research [17], as they are easy to work with and relatively high-performing. In this article, the opportunity to leverage their favorable mechanical properties for building the autophage launcher's combustable structure is analyzed.

Fig. 2. Annotated Schematic of an early autophage concept from [3].

First, the fundamental governing principles of autophage space propulsion are presented. The main objective of this article is then addressed, namely evaluating the potential for advancing the maturity of hybrid autophage launcher technology via a comparative analysis, contrasting the key performance aspects of autophage launcher architecture with those of several state-of-the-art launch systems. Additionally, this article will delve into the specific challenges associated with autophage launcher architecture. It aims to outline prospective research efforts to respond to these challenges. Alpha Impulsion currently breaks down these perceived efforts into three consecutive projects.

2. Specifics of autophage rockets

The fundamental architectural features that set autophage propulsion apart from other methods are explored, with emphasis laid on identifying the key design parameters necessary for describing and modeling the propulsion system.

2.1 Basic governing principles

Modern autophage propulsion relies on utilizing the launcher's structure as reaction mass. The selection of the structural propellant is crucial for any autophage architecture. For a given fairing and rocket engine, the cross section of the combustible structure is set, leaving its length as a degree of freedom. In the case of a simple cylindrical shape, the propellant mass M_p is then limited only by the maximum aspect ratio allowable. With ρ_m as the mean density of the propellant and D the main body diameter:

$$M_p = \rho_m L \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \quad (1)$$

Considering a hollow cylinder of external radius r , length L and thickness t , made of solid fuel (density ρ_{fu}), containing a cylindrical volume of oxidizer (density ρ_{ox}), the mean density of propellants can be calculated

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_m L \pi r^2 &= \rho_{ox} L \pi (r-t)^2 + \rho_{fu} L \pi (r^2 - (r-t)^2) \\ \rho_m &= \rho_{ox} (1-t/r)^2 + \rho_{fu} (1 - (1-t/r)^2) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

From Tsiolkovsky's equation:

$$\Delta V = I_{sp} \ln \left(\frac{M_i}{M_e + M_u} \right) \quad (3)$$

where $M_i = M_p + M_e + M_u$ is the lift-off mass of the rocket, M_e is the mass of the engine and M_u is the remaining non-reacting mass (upper structure, leftover fuel, fairing and payload). It appears theoretically that any value of ΔV is attainable by adjusting the mass of propellant because it is independent from the dry mass.

In practice, the increase in required thrust to take off limits the maximum lift-off weight.

Considering the acceleration at lift-off $\gamma = T/M_i$, Tsiolkovsky's equation can be re-arranged to integrate the thrust limitation of the engine:

$$\frac{M_u}{M_i} = \exp \left(-\frac{\Delta V}{I_{sp}} \right) - \gamma \frac{M_e}{T} \quad (4)$$

For a given ΔV requirement, the upper mass fraction of the rocket M_u/M_i increases with decreasing acceleration at lift-off γ , increasing engine thrust-to-weight ratio T/M_e and increasing I_{sp} .

2.2 Propellant insertion system

The velocity at which propellants are fed to the chamber is named autophage velocity v_a in this article or propellant feed rate in other literature.

This velocity can be expressed in terms of aspect ratio as well, $\dot{f} = v_a/D$. From the variation in propellants mass, the thrust can be expressed

$$T = \dot{m} I_{sp} = I_v v_a \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \quad (5)$$

where I_{sp} and I_v denote the specific and volumetric specific impulse of the engine (in S.I. units). From this, controlling propellant insertion via v_a becomes key to both maintaining nominal thrust and throttling the engine.

To achieve this goal, the chamber pressure must be overcome by a mechanical system powerful enough to insert the propellants. With an external linear actuator as a first attempt in this direction, Yemets *et al.* observed a response of the chamber pressure and thrust to mechanical forcing of the propellant rod into the engine [8]. For the hybrid autophage engine, a forced insertion mechanism could enable control over the total flow rate. This implies control over solid regression rate thanks to the oxidizer flux, full mass flow rate and consequently thrust. Several mechanisms have been proposed to achieve linear motion of the propellants into the chamber, such as:

- inertial feeding: the action of the thrust against the inertia of the propellant itself [3, 10],
- an electric winch [4, 10], rack-and-pinion [4, 18], or lead screw [18] (similar concepts with long parts),
- axially oriented pistons successively filled with hot gas (the nozzle coolant) [18],
- a short electric lead screw engaged in the solid propellant itself as presented in this article,
- evolution of the present work for the short lead screw: add a pump to increase combustion pressure and/or replace the electric feed with a turbine and tap-off or expander cycle for mass performance.

Schematics are available in cited sources.

The power required for this insertion system P_{ins} is directly linked to the thrust, performance, and chamber pressure p_{ch} of the engine,

$$P_{ins} = p_{ch} v_a \frac{\pi D^2}{4} = \frac{p_{ch}}{I_v} T \quad (6)$$

A concept for propellants insertion by a lead-screw lead by an electric motor and batteries (see Fig. 3) is presented. This architecture was chosen by the criteria of specific power and efficiency against a winch coursing through the grain and a rack and pinion system formed by the grain itself and a motor respectively. The solid fuel has to be actively inserted into the combustion chamber. The

lead screw system is very simple and can be interesting if its performance is reasonable.

Fig. 3. Schematic of the Lead screw inserting the fuel by an electric motor system in a hybrid autophage engine.

The insertion motor drives the screw that turns in the threaded fuel. The rocket engine is then connected with the insertion motor with a beam that passes through the fuel grain. This link is permanent and will cut the fuel as it gets inserted into the combustion chamber, that's the reason the beam is chosen to have the shape of thin knives. These knives are crucial: they play the role of stator and free-run stop in the lead screw system, preventing the grain from rotating with the screw.

3. Choice of Propellants

In autophage concepts, the solid propellants shall combine interesting combustion performance and sufficient mechanical properties to act as the structure. For calculations, one considers a non-cohesive propellant – powdered solid or liquid – contained within the hollow cylindrical shape formed by the solid propellant. The first step in the definition of an autophage launcher is the choice of the oxidizer, the fuel, and their mixing ratio. Most solids considered are thermoplastics, they are at the center of existing literature in hybrid propulsion research, known for generally showing good combustion performance. They also show excellent mechanical characteristics, a requirement that tends to disqualify HTPB and paraffin as main autophage propulsion fuels. Nuances of polyethylene (low density, high density, ultra high molecular weight, blends), ABS, Polypropylene, and less com-

mon blends are considered, with possible energetic additives Oxidizers considered are non-cohesive, with a limitation as to their toxicity (see Fig. 8 for main couples considered).

3.1 Geometrical considerations

In autophage propulsion, the average O/F ratio over the flight is related to the geometry of the engine. The propellants both have an insertion velocity $v_a = \dot{m}_p / A_p / \rho_m$ (See Fig. 7). The average insertion velocity of both propellants should be the same, to prevent a situation where one propellant has been exhausted and the other remains as dead weight. Their instantaneous velocity however, could be different at a given time. Considering the cylinder case again, the mass of fuel is computed as $M_{fu} = \rho_{fu} L \pi (r^2 - (r-t)^2)$. Similarly, the mass of oxidizer is $M_{ox} = \rho_{ox} L \pi (r-t)^2$. The average O/F ratio must thus be equal to

$$O/F = \frac{M_{ox}}{M_{fu}} = \frac{\rho_{ox} (r/t - 1)^2}{\rho_{fu} 2r/t - 1} \quad (7)$$

3.2 Propellants regression

In all autophage engine, a solid structure must be vaporized to be used as reaction gas in a rocket nozzle. Depending on the solution of vaporization chosen, the regression rate \dot{r} , defined as the speed at which a pyrolyzing surface burns away, limits the autophage velocity allowable in the engine. A high regression rate thus enables a high autophage velocity, with typical regression rate being between 1 mm/s and 10 mm/s. The regression rate is governed by the heating of the propellant until it reaches pyrolysis temperature. The thermal conductivity, heat capacity and pyrolysis temperature of the propellant are thus values of interest.

Modern autophage design always rely on a regression surface larger than the propellant rod cross-section to increase the allowable autophage velocity. In Fig. 6 and 7, it is a simple cone geometry. With a cone half-angle ψ , the autophage velocity is

$$v_a = \frac{\dot{r}}{\sin(\psi)} \quad (8)$$

3.3 Summary graph

Following the previous analysis, Fig. 4 summarizes possible propellant combinations for autophage launchers. AlH3 is considered as an additive capable of being mixed with the solid fuel, accounting for 20% of the total mass of the grain, and serves as a depiction of advanced formulations of grains to estimate potential performance of the couple. The hydrogen peroxide considered here is at 98% concentration. As mechanical performance

is of great importance, the grain (or combustible structure) aspect ratio is plotted against characteristic velocity (obtained from NASA's Chemical Equilibrium Analysis). It corresponds to the aspect ratio at which the structure shows equivalent dynamic response to an estimate of the structure of Falcon 9 FT (explained in detail in the next section). Here, several propellants induce near equivalent theoretical combustion performance to LOX/RP-1, and produce structures stiff enough to allow thinner launchers. See Fig. 8 for I_{sp} results.

Fig. 4. Overview of possible autophage propellants: aspect ratio for same α as Falcon 9 FT [dotted] (see Table 1). The curves evolve with O/F ratio variations until optimal c^* .

4. Comparison to the state of the art

A first attempt has been made in this article to compare different contemporary state-of-the-art launch systems and a potential commercial hybrid autophage launcher.

Our focus will primarily revolve around identifying and assessing key parameters governing launcher subsystems performance. Our objective is to ensure that the conclusions derived from our calculations accurately reflect the reality of primary design choices, in order to expose advantages and limits of a hybrid autophage architecture.

4.1 Structure

This discussion is a preliminary discussion evaluating the viability of a cryogenic thermoplastic structure for the hybrid autophage launcher when confronted to dynamic loads during operations. To begin with, static requirements can be dismissed relatively fast. Indeed, the autophage tank has very thick walls brought by the geometrical O/F ratio. For Grenat launcher (inputs below and in Table 4), this results in a burst pressure of 210 bar according to the thick cylinder theory, using Tresca criterion for an expected yield stress of cryogenic polyethylene at 140

MPa (see Fig. 9). Similarly, largely acceptable results can be found for the main directions of mechanical loading.

A more pressing requirement is to ensure limited dynamic response. While no direct results can be presented at this point as satisfying mechanical loads models applied to autophage structures are lacking, a comparison of parameters driving the response of the structure between launchers can help evaluating the viability of the autophage structure. The structure is approximated to one dimensional beam under transversal loads, as can be the case considering gusts of wind in flight and on the launch pad. For a beam of aspect ratio $f = L/2r$ and cross section $S = \pi(r^2 - (r-t)^2)$, with y the deflection and $q(x,t)$ the applied force per unit length, the Euler–Bernoulli beam theory provides the following

$$EI \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + \rho S \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} = q \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial^4 \bar{w}}{\partial \bar{x}^4} + \frac{\partial^2 \bar{w}}{\partial \bar{t}^2} = \bar{q} \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{w} = w/L$, $\bar{x} = x/L$, $\bar{t} = t/\sqrt{\frac{\mu f}{\alpha}}$, and $\bar{q} = q/(2r\alpha)$ are dimensionless parameters. The response amplitude is fully governed by \bar{q} , and thus for a given lateral pressure $q/2r$ by the factor α , which represents stiffness or flexural rigidity allowing comparison between launchers of different sizes.

$$\alpha = \frac{EI}{16f^3 r^4} = \frac{\pi E(1 - (1-t/r)^4)}{64f^3} \quad (11)$$

For a given α ,

$$f = \left(\frac{EI}{16\alpha r^4} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (12)$$

with f the aspect ratio for a given value of α . Now an acceptable value of α is needed to compare to the sizing of autophage launchers envisaged. This value should be obtained from existing launchers.

In Table 1, first results are given for autophage launchers, namely Lapis-Lazuli the small demonstrator developed by Alpha Impulsion, and the commercial micro-launcher Grenat. An autophage structure with high aspect ratio usually means better aerodynamic characteristics as well as a lower structural mass for the rocket engine. This incentive makes the stiffness requirement increasingly important, as a thinner rocket will undergo higher bending stresses due to aerodynamic and elastic effects. Still, the structural part of Grenat was sized with $f = 18.4$ (full launcher: $f = 20.8$, see Table 4).

The structure of Falcon 9, like most launchers, is more complex than a simple tube. For simplification, its monocoque liquid oxygen tanks is considered. Indeed, fuel

tanks are usually stiffened, and skirts are used complexifying the stiffness calculation. A rough estimate is made for F9FT based on the LOx tank characteristics only, applied to the full length of the structure.

	F9FT estimate	Lapis-Lazuli	Grenat
Material	2195 Al-Li	PE	PE
E (GPa)	77	6*	6*
r (m)	1.83	0.45	0.45
t (mm)	$\lesssim 5$	66.2	66.2
L (m)	56.6	8,7	16,6**
r/t	366	6.80	6.80
α (Pa)	$1.1 \cdot 10^4$	$1.5 \cdot 10^5$	$2.2 \cdot 10^4$
f	15.5	9.7	18.4

Table 1. Evaluation of autophage launchers stiffness and rough attempt at comparing with state of the art (* See Fig. 9; ** Length of the combustible structure; source F9: SpaceX)

The results show $\alpha = 1.5 \cdot 10^5$ for the current sizing for Lapis-Lazuli. It would then be more than ten times stiffer than Falcon 9 and would be less sensible dynamic loads, or could be sized thinner to increase performance. The same conclusion is drawn for the current sizing of Grenat with $\alpha = 2.2 \cdot 10^4$, twice that of Falcon 9. Payload fraction could be increased by increasing this aspect ratio, but further studies are needed to identify the risks for a really thinner, more flexible launcher, notably the limits of a thrust vectoring system. Plus, the calculated aspect ratio only holds for the beginning of the flight, and as the launcher consumes itself it will become sturdier. At max q, the launcher will already have consumed a significant part of its length, about 25% for Grenat (result from a non-presented work, part of future publications). This constitutes an other source of margin for sturdier or thinner launchers. The presented approach is preliminary and will go on during the future works dedicated to Lapis-Lazuli and Grenat.

As an intermediate conclusion, it is noted that average nuances of polyethylene result in quite stiff launchers at equivalent aspect ratio, and is already regarded as interesting material, among others. Autophage launchers longer, thinner than usual are possible, contributing to the potential payload performance of this architecture. Other opportunities exist to improve this situation, with fiber additives able to adjust the mechanical behaviour, or better base materials. Ultra high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) for instance could improve mechanics without changing the combustion performance.

4.2 Insertion

The lead screw assembly is compared to propellant pumps, used in classic engine architectures, with respect to efficiency and specific power. On the Ambre experimental rocket (first demonstrator of Alpha Impulsion), the input power of the lead screw system is 1500 W, with an output of 300 W, leading to an efficiency of 0.2. This can be explained by the relatively low lead screw angle of 4.6° and large friction coefficient between polyethylene and aluminum at 0.2. Having a weight of 3 kg, the specific power of the system implemented on Ambre is 100 W/kg. This low scale, experimental design is a non-optimized basis from which to improve and bring the system to values closer to competing technologies such as propellant pumps. By working with various low friction materials, such as PTFE coatings or UHMWPE, the specific power of a lead screw insertion system could be improved substantially. These friction coefficients in the range of 0.05-0.1 lead to efficiencies up to 0.85 in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Lead screw efficiency for various friction coefficients between solid fuel and the system, as well as various lead screw angle. The effect of knives are negligible for pressure above 50 bar.

The sizing of pumps rely on two design choices: a specific speed and a specific diameter. The ideal geometrical parameters for best efficiency are described by Cordier's on Balje's diagram and depend on these choices. In practice, specific power values often lie in a limited range for actual rocket engines.

Complete turbopumps assemblies usually show specific power of 10 to 20 kW/kg in existing systems. The specific power of pumps are thus greater, with efficiencies often close to 0.7 [19, 20, 21].

As an intermediate conclusion, the lead screw is expected to allow for a power efficiency on par with pump, possibly greater if well optimized, leading to an equiva-

	Efficiency	Power density
Lead screw	0.4 - 0.9	> 100W/kg
Centrifugal pump	0.6 - 0.7	> 10kW/kg

Table 2. Efficiency and power density comparison for the solid insertion system.

lent requirement on the sizing of the power source (see next section). However, the early small scale design shows poor power density, and could not compare to larger pumps. Further work is needed to evaluate the specific power of a mature system. At small scale at least, the lead-screw seems to fall behind.

The lead screw needs to account for the solid fuel insertion and cutting, and some of its power must be allocated to insert the liquid oxidizer into its feeding system based on the tank pressure. By taking into account the knives' output work as well as the penetration work and the friction work on three different surfaces, the required cutting force can be computed as well as the total screw efficiency. The cutting and the friction work of the knives have been evaluated with models from [22] (chapter 5). This total force strongly depends on surface temperature. First estimations were made for the first demonstrator (AMBRE) at ambient temperature. The cutting force accounts for approximately 10% of the total available power of the screw, while fuel insertion accounts for 40%. This work shall be expanded by experimentation, and no further results are presentable. However, the trend of these calculations show that the share of the cutting force will decrease as the rocket considered grows larger, until they are negligible for mini-launchers and larger.

4.3 Engine cycle

In this section, the electric-fed cycle, the full flow expander cycle, the expander bleed cycle, the tap-off cycle and the gas generator cycle are quickly compared, and their applicability to hybrid and autophage engines is discussed. The two main characteristics we are looking for in those cycles are the power density and the specific impulse efficiency (in the case of a bleed cycle).

In electric-fed engines, all of the propellant is pumped by an external electric-powered system, it is thus a full flow cycle with no I_{sp} loss. Brushless electric motors specific power is generally between 4 to 8 kW/kg for $\eta = 0.8$, with an inverter of 60kW/kg and $\eta = 0.85$ [19]; as for batteries, the best candidate found features $P_s = 6.95kW/kg$ [20] (with discharge rate corresponding to the burn time of a first stage of a classical launcher). In total, this amounts to a power density between 3 and 4kW/kg.

The gas generator cycle is a bleed cycle, where a small

percentage of the main flow is burned in a dedicated gas generator to drive the turbine. In addition to the I_{sp} loss from the exhausted fuel, the added mass of the gas generator lowers the power density of the system. Specific powers for complete turbopump assemblies are between 10 and 20kW/kg [23], thus turbine on their own possess an even greater specific power. Using [24], it was approximated a value of 8kW/kg for the gas generator, leading to a complete gas generator plus turbine power density around 5 to 6 kW/kg.

With an expander cycle, the heat from a regenerative cooling circuit is used to drive a turbine. The gases are then either exhausted (bleed cycle) or fed into the combustion chamber (full flow cycle). Depending on the case, this cycle features a specific impulse efficiency of either unity or lower. For the bleed cycle, the quantity of exhausted fuel amounts for 10-15% of the total mass flow [25, 26, 27]. When one considers the total mass flow, the bled exhaust falls around 2 to 3%. For the calculation of the power density, the regenerative cooling will not be considered, as they are an integral part of the thermal protection design of the chamber. The total power density of the system is thus equal to that of the turbine (greater than 10kW/kg). The close coupling between the thermal protection design and turbine design of this cycle imposes hard limits on the maximum power and size available. In particular, the combustion chamber surface area exposed to hot gases is an important criteria.

Finally, the tap-off cycle is considered, where a small percentage of the main flow is tapped off the combustion chamber to drive a turbine. It is also a bleed cycle, incurring a small loss in I_{sp} . Where this cycle excels however is in the power density, as it relies only on a turbine with no added components. We can thus consider power densities greater than 10kW/kg, as for the expander cycle. In practice, without limitations on the heat carried by the working fluid, tap-off cycles have increased turbine efficiencies.

	I_{sp} efficiency	Power density
Electric-fed	100 %	3 - 4 kW/kg
Gas generator	93 - 98.5 %	5 - 6 kW/kg
Expander bleed	97 - 98 %	> 10kW/kg
Expander full flow	100 %	> 10kW/kg
Tap-off	-	≫ 10kW/kg

Table 3. Comparison of I_{sp} and power densities

Most small scale hybrid engine rely on pressurizing gas to pressurize their oxidizer tank. At a launch vehicle scale, the electric-fed cycle is the most common, as it is relatively simple and fully compatible with the hybrid architecture. The expander cycle (whether bleed or full flow), if used, must be able to work off the heat of the

post-combustion chamber and the nozzle only, as the rest of the chamber is protected by the fuel grain. Additionally, as classical hybrid rocket engine use a liquid oxidizer, it is the oxidizer that must be used as heat-bearing fluid, lowering the cycle's efficiency. The gas generator cycle is difficult to use with hybrid engines, as only one propellant can be fed into the generator. An additional tank, containing a liquid fuel, must be used to feed the generator and power this cycle. Finally, the tap-off cycle is in theory fully applicable to hybrid engines, provided there is a way to pipe the exhaust. Few engines however are being developed based on this cycle, which is very difficult to master.

Autophage hybrid engine share the same characteristics with a classical hybrid engine on every point, with one added difficulty. In the most simple case, without a central body, it is extremely difficult with this architecture to pipe out the exhaust (barring the use of any bleed cycle), or to regeneratively cool any part of the chamber (removing the option of an expander cycle). The only reasonable concept seems to be an electric-fed cycle. This changes in the case of a central body geometry, making it possible to exhaust the turbine's gases while also providing a large area to heat the propellant for expander cycles.

4.4 Vaporization

In this section, the minimum chamber size needs to be calculated to ensure good combustion and vaporization inside the chamber. Four cases are considered: bi-liquid combustion, hybrid combustion, Promin Aerospace's gasification and hybrid autophage combustion.

In the case of bi-liquid combustion, the length of the chamber depends on a characteristic chamber length $L^* = V_{ch}/A_{throat}$. The characteristic chamber length is given for a specific propellant combination [28], and obtained by experiment. The diameter is calculated to ensure a proper contraction ratio $CR = A_{ch}/A_{throat}$. The main obstacle to low contraction ratio are Rayleigh line losses, increasing with big chamber gas Mach number. A common contraction ratio is around 2.5, and a margin should be kept to the limit of 1 [27].

In the solid concept by Yemets *et al.*, regression is dominated by heat transfer from a hot conductive contact surface. This intermediary, called the vaporizer, is put between the hot gases of the combustion chamber and the incoming propellants. The hot metallic vaporizer heat the propellants as they arrive, vaporizing them and conducting the resulting hot gases through segregated channels in the vaporizer to an injection ring. The key physical phenomenon to be studied in this paragraph is thus the heat transfer from the metallic surface to the fuel and oxidizer and the enthalpy of vaporization of the propellants to de-

termine possible regression rate for the fuel.

Fig. 6. Regression model in current solid autophage engines design (nozzle is to the right)

Fig. 7. Regression model in the hybrid autophage engine (nozzle is to the right)

The regression rate of this architecture can be estimated by looking at experimental data from [8]. Propellant feed rate (or autophage speed) of $600\text{mm}/\text{min}$ ($10\text{mm}/\text{s}$) have been achieved by an engine with a half-cone angle around 9° , with no significant surcharge on the insertion system. The final regression rate lies around $1.6\text{mm}/\text{s}$. To increase this regression rate, an increase in temperature differential (between the fuel grain and the vaporizer) can be applied, but this is limited by our current knowledge of high temperature material. Another method is to increase the heat transfer coefficient between the two, by increasing the insertion force for example.

In the hybrid concept, the classical process of pyrolysis by the diffusion flame occurs, which can be described by Marxman's simplified law, applying to Fig. 7:

$$\dot{r} = a(G_{ox})^n, G_{ox} = \rho_{ox}v_a \quad (13)$$

For hybrid combustion, the size of the combustion chamber is not defined by the characteristic combustion length, but rather by the needed combustion area for a given thrust. For simple single-port grain, the combustion area increases from $S_c^0 = 2\pi r^0 L_g$ to $S_c^1 = 2\pi r^1 L_g$. At any given time, Marxman's law tell us the regression rate of the fuel grain, defined by its empirical form $\dot{r} = aG_{ox}^n$. The length, initial diameter and final diameter of the fuel grain is computed from the design thrust curve. At the end of the fuel grain, a small post-combustion chamber is

necessary to ensure good mixing and combustion of the propellant.

In the case of autophage propulsion, two different cases are considered. The first one is considering a similar architecture to hybrid, albeit with new fuel being constantly fed from the top. In this case, Marxman's law is still applicable, giving us the regression rate of the fuel. As it enters the chamber, the grain will thus burn thinner and thinner, until all of it has been combusted. This chamber length L_{ch} is defined by the regression characteristics.

At the first order, the grain's aspect ratio in the chamber is defined as:

$$f_{ch} = \frac{L_{ch}}{2r} = \frac{t}{2r} \frac{v_a}{\dot{r}} \quad (14)$$

Using Marxman's law to express the regression rate (assuming constant port diameter equal to the initial fuel internal diameter):

$$f_{ch} = \frac{t}{r} \frac{v_a^{1-n}}{2a\rho_{ox}^n} \quad (15)$$

Generally, $n < 1$, meaning that the regressing grain length or aspect ratio increases with increasing autophage velocity. This effect is less pronounced when n approaches 1, the value at which the chamber aspect ratio is constant (no matter is autophage velocity). The thrust (i.e. autophage velocity v_a) will have a small impact on the necessary combustion chamber size, growing to the power of $1 - n$. Regardless of the autophage velocity, the combustion chamber size (and mass) grows with the cube of the diameter, leading us to prefer long and thin structure to be burned in a hybrid autophage combustion chamber.

Finally, the case of a hybrid autophage combustion with a central body is considered. This central body can be used to optimize the injection of oxidizer in the chamber, as well as increase the oxidizer mass flux G_{ox} . For bodies forming an angle ψ in respect to the launcher axis, an equilibrium forms. A low regression rate leads to the fuel getting closer to the wall, increasing the mass flux and the regression rate until an equilibrium is found. The presence of a central body and this phenomenon enable higher oxidizer mass flux in the chamber, higher regression rates and smaller combustion chamber. One limit exists: the maximum Mach of the flow inside the chamber and Rayleigh line losses. Let us consider the combustion chamber area A_{ch} . One can compute the oxidizer flux as $G_{ox} = \dot{m}_{ox}/A_{ch}$ and the regression rate as $\dot{r} = aG_{ox}^n = a(\dot{m}_{ox}/A_{ch})^n$. At equilibrium, the regression rate \dot{r} compensate the arrival of incoming fuel at autophage speed v_a . At first order, the equation becomes $\dot{r} = v_a \cdot \sin(\psi)$ with a constant combustion chamber area A_{ch} . Finally, considering the equations between chamber pressure, throat area

and mass flow, one gets the contraction ratio

$$CR = A_{ch}/A_{throat} = \frac{O/F}{1 + O/F} \frac{p_{ch}}{C^*} \left(\frac{a}{v_a \cdot \sin(\psi)} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (16)$$

Depending on the smallest contraction ratio allowable, the autophage speed is thus limited to:

$$v_a = \frac{a}{\sin(\psi)} \left(\frac{O/F}{1 + O/F} \frac{p_{ch}}{CR \cdot C^*} \right)^n \quad (17)$$

4.5 Combustion

The combustion performance of the propellants can be summarized by their characteristic velocity C^* and specific heat ratio γ , the only two parameters needed to compute the specific impulse – given nozzle parameters. In this section, thermochemical performance of propellant combinations are compared, by computing a representative specific impulse in vacuum I_{vac} at a chamber pressure of 100 bar for a vacuum-optimized nozzle with an expansion ratio equal to 200. CEArun is used to provide ideal values in the case of complete combustion for a given O/F mass ratio.

Fig. 8. Ranking of propellants couples vacuum specific impulse for a chamber pressure of 100 bar and a nozzle expansion ratio of 200.

Several families are identified related to the performance of their respective oxidizer and shown Fig. 8: liquid oxygen, N2O4, H2O2, and various solid oxidizers. For liquid oxidizer, the choice of fuel dictates the

Launcher	Falcon 9 FT	Firefly Alpha	Electron	SL1	OB-1 Mk1	Zaarbird	Lapis Lazuli	Grenat
Company	SpaceX	Firefly Aerospace	Rocket Lab	HyImpulse	HyPrSpace	Promin Aerospace	Alpha Impulsion	Alpha Impulsion
Total mass (t)	587	54	12.7	36	-	2.5	6.4	12.7
Rocket engine	Merlin 1D+	Reaver / Lightning	Rutherford	HyPLOX75/ HyPLOX10	-	-	-	-
T_{engine} (kN)	845	184 / 70.1	21.3	75 / 10	100	11	73	191
Structure	Metallic	Composite	Composite	Composite	Composite	Autophage	Autophage	Autophage
Total L/D ratio (no boosters)	18.5	15.9	10.1	12.7	13.7	17.8	12.1	20.8
Mean structural index	4.1%	7.7%	7.1%	11.3%	-	-	1.90%	2.14%
Insertion	Pump	Pump	Pump	Pump	Pump	Wheels	Lead screw	Screw+pump
P_{ch} (bar)	108	80	100	60 / 11.5	-	-	46	100
Engine cycle	Gas Generator	Tap-off	Electric-fed	Gas Generator	-	-	Electric-fed	Closed expander
Vaporization	Bi-liquid	Bi-liquid	Bi-liquid	Hybrid	Hybrid	Vaporizer	Autophage hybrid	Same + central body
Combustion	LOX/RP-1	LOX/RP-1	LOX/RP-1	LOX/Paraffin	LOX/PE	AP/AN/PE	LOX/PE	LOX/PE/AIH3
O/F ratio	2.36	-	-	3.0	-	-	2.9 / 3.1	2.3 / 2.5
C_{theor}^* (m/s)	1816	-	-	1761 / 1725	-	-	1741 / 1779	1808 / 1789
Nozzle	Bell nozzle	Bell nozzle	Bell nozzle	Bell nozzle	Plug nozzle	Plug nozzle	Bell nozzle	Pintle+Plug
ϵ_{sea}	21	-	-	16	-	-	60	50
ϵ_{vac}	165	-	-	30	-	-	60	300
Theor. $C_{F,sea}$	1.66	-	-	1.60	-	-	1.33	1.99
Theor. $C_{F,vac}$	2.01	-	-	1.96	-	-	2.04	2.15
Synthesis								
$\eta_{Isp,sea}$	95%	-	-	94%	-	-	94%	94%
$I_{sp,sea}$ (s)	2844	2903	3050	2648	-	-	2170	3386
$\eta_{Isp,vac}$	93%	-	-	91%	-	-	94%	94%
$I_{sp,vac}$ (s)	3413	3158	3364	3069	-	-	3350	3650
$TWR_{mot,sea}$	184	94	72.8	> 53	-	-	46	59
Payload fraction to LEO	3.9%	< 1.4%	1.9%	1.4%	(est. < 2%)	0.3%	2%	3.9%

Table 4. Comparison of several launch vehicles (dash: data not obtained)

final performance, with most of the time the following order: Methane, RP-1, Paraffin, PE and ABS. This is coherent with the properties of each hydrocarbon. The performance difference between fuels is exacerbated when using liquid oxygen, but quite small when considering other oxidizers.

It is clear that polymers have comparable performances to other hydrocarbons, with potential to reach high theoretical specific impulses. Despite this, hybrid rocket engine especially, have suffered performance issues and encountered low combustion efficiencies. This problem has been worked on and almost eradicated lately, giving birth to several commercial projects.

5. Technical challenges and future works

5.1 Timeline

Alpha Impulsion proposes to raise the TRL of hybrid autophage propulsion from 2 to 7 with 3 consecutive projects. Ambre is an experimental rocket of 1kN thrust with catalytic injection of High-test Peroxide (HTP) on HDPE, meant to demonstrate autophage propulsion fast

at a small scale in 2024. This rocket will allow to test the validity of the concepts presented in this article: geometrical O/F, insertion balance, insertion mechanism and dynamic chamber sealing. Following, Lapis Lazuli is a cryogenic demonstrator meant to bring the TRL to 5 within 3 to 4 years, with sufficient control over LOX-PE autophage propulsion to perform suborbital flights. Most of central research works on combustion, insertion and structure are condensed in this project. A theoretical orbital version of Lapis Lazuli is presented in the Table 4. Then, Grenat is sized as a proper hybrid autophage commercial launcher with a 500 kg payload capacity.

5.2 Thermoplastic cryogenic tanks

Manufacturing a cryogenic combustible structure is a primary challenge in achieving orbital hybrid autophage propulsion. Key questions include whether a solid fuel can withstand flight and insertion stresses below its glass transition temperature due to liquid oxygen, endure vibrations, after resisting the cooling process. Fig. 9 offers data on mechanical properties, with an emphasis on

Fig. 9. Mechanical properties of thermoplastics of interest at low temperature [32, 33, 34].

the modulus of elasticity's rise at cryogenic temperatures, which contributes to allow higher launcher aspect ratios as was discussed in the above. As temperature drops, polymers become stronger but more brittle, often leading to fracture as the primary failure mode, highlighting the importance of toughness [29]. Data on cryogenic toughness remains limited (to the authors' knowledge), but emerging applications in fields like liquid natural gas suggest promising materials, such as UHMWPE, showing superior properties [30]. Chemical compatibility with liquid oxygen varies; while PE and ABS are generally incompatible with it according to ASTM G86 standard, showing impact reactivity [31], fluoropolymers liners like polytetrafluoroethylene show potential in solving this issue. Extensive testing is required to confirm initial findings, and dynamic behavior under low temperatures is yet to be addressed. In the mean time the sealing of the cryogenic thermoplastic structured tank isn't addressed in this article and shall be seriously investigated in future works. These challenges are central to our efforts in developing the cryogenic suborbital demonstrator Lapis Lazuli, through rigorous material characterization, structural simulation, and testing in cryogenic environments.

5.3 Single-stage-to-orbit performance

The autophage concept is an alternative to staged rockets, solving the problem of excessive dry mass. However,

Fig. 10. Altitude compensating capability of the Aerospike nozzle [28].

single-stage-to-orbit vehicles (thus single engine to orbit) face several challenges associated with their wide range of environments. At sea-level, the engine and nozzle must provide high thrust despite the ambient atmospheric pressure. In vacuum, the engine must then provide lower thrust (to keep the acceleration bounded) and high efficiency by taking advantage of the vacuum environment to expand its exhaust gases as much as possible.

These requirements call for solutions unrelated with the autophage concept, but they represent a research topic paramount to SSTO development: variable geometry nozzle and nozzle adaptation (plug nozzle, aerospike, pintle nozzle, etc.), their performance are shown Fig. 10. Typically, several bell nozzles on several stages allow for several curves to approach that of the aerospike, but this is not possible here.

Therefore, when the basics of hybrid autophage propulsion are characterized and a high combustion efficiency cryogenic engine is successfully operated in suborbital flights, validating TRL5, the major challenge of erasing the SSTO's shortcomings will remain to reach full performance. The issue of nozzle adaptation is a common challenge in the field. It results in a performance loss that must be addressed for the success of a SSTO concept. Further research is required before developing a high performance launcher. One potential solution is the annular Aerospike nozzle, which is gaining traction in the private propulsion industry [35] with recent firing tests. Another example for adaptation and expansion ratio is a variable throat area with a pintle nozzle, often studied in solid propulsion [36]. While challenges like separated flow regions and inefficiencies exist, efforts are be-

ing made to mitigate them [37, 38, 39]. These solutions are still at low technology readiness levels and they are not a primary concern for autophage propulsion maturation, but their investigation appears necessary for a commercial project.

5.4 Maximum acceleration

Acceleration constraints are also one of the staple of SSTO vehicles. A deep throttle with stable combustion at low flow rates is necessary – with requirements as low as 15% of the take-off thrust (throttling factor of 6.7 : 1). In the case of hybrid propulsion, this means the engine should be designed with a nominal oxidizer flux high enough to be throttled down without causing combustion instabilities. This requirement is not particularly demanding. Indeed, values in the range of $G_{ox} \in [500; 700] kg.m^{-2}.s^{-1}$ are typically found as a maximum attainable design value [40], with exceptions going higher [41]. From this range, throttling down to 15% of the nominal value would imply a requirement for stable combustion at $G_{ox} \approx 75 kg.m^{-2}.s^{-1}$, which is quite commonly attained [42]. A remaining challenge is to scale up from lab-scale engines and sounding rockets, as larger grain ports tend to decrease the oxidizer flux [43]. Aside from stability concerns, deep throttling in hybrid propulsion is usually submitted to the O/F-shift phenomenon, which can cause performance drops of several percents [44]. An observation can be made about the autophage case: the disturbance in O/F provoked by throttling tends to reduce with time, going back to the geometrical O/F value, which could mitigate the performance loss. In Fig. 11, a theoretical example has been plotted. The autophage velocity v_a is controlled (equivalent to controlling the insertion actuator), and results shown come from basic modeling of the O/F ratio during time, with Marxman's law governing regression and 15 describing the shape of the regression surface. As can be suspected from the O/F response to basic v_a laws, precise control over the variation of v_a will allow to keep O/F at a constant value slightly lower than the initial value. Typically the characteristic time of variation of O/F is several seconds or tens of seconds. This indicates that to achieve constant O/F throughout the flight, throttling must be made gradually to allow the combustion surface shape enough time to adapt.

5.5 Engine cycle

The high regression needed to reduce the combustion chamber size and the need for higher pressure, higher performance combustion. The addition of a central body inside the combustion chamber would allow better channeling of the oxidizer for a higher G_{ox} and regression rate. Using the cryogenic oxidizer as a coolant then becomes central. This method will demand a pump to support the

Fig. 11. Preliminary view of the effects of throttling with control over v_a . Results are non-dimensional (inputs for HTP87.5/PE, $O/F_{init} = 4.83$).

pressure losses, complementing the more basic incentive for a high chamber pressure, allowing better pressure ratios. There is an opportunity to bring the oxygen to a super-critical state, avoiding the added complexity of liquid injection or even allowing swirl injection. [44]. For larger launchers (limit yet to be drawn), an expander or tap-off cycle can draw on this opportunity to enable lighter insertion systems.

Other options can be considered. Pursuing a very light SSTO with suboptimal nozzle efficiency could for example lead to a viable, very inexpensive launcher. The lack of experimental results leave this discussion open-ended. This is the focus of the Lapis Lazuli project, which aims to assess the performance of a simple single-stage launcher.

5.6 Cost estimation

This article does not cover the necessary work to be done on cost estimating, one of the greatest prospect of autophage propulsion. Preliminary calculations on the subject have shown that the reduced stage and part count will lead to a great difference in manufacturing cost, as well as manufacturing environmental impact. In most cases, comparative cost analyses have proven insufficient to cover the radically different autophage architecture (except for the most basic cases, such as the fairing and avionics). On the other hand, design and experimental work are not sufficiently advanced to provide a good basis for a bottom-up analysis. However, a quick discussion on radically different cost items can point at the main

stakes. Traditional tanks are removed, both in manufacturing and logistics, and replaced by a large solid propellant part possibly produced near or at the launch site. The production of propellants is usually relatively inexpensive when compared to manufactured parts, but results show that it plays a significant role in the environmental cost of a launcher life cycle [45]. An opportunity is identified to make viable the use of recycled polymers in the combustible structure. Stage separation is also removed, along with its complex product assurance and testing. Stages themselves with different engines are not needed. On the other hand, the solid insertion system is a new concept and difficulties can be discovered that will increase its complexity and cost. The preliminary assessment show several key advantages that tend to present hybrid autophage propulsion as a promising, inexpensive architecture.

6. Conclusions

Hybrid autophage propulsion for space launch vehicles is introduced. This novel concept shows impressive preliminary results: the resulting micro-launcher features a payload fraction equivalent to that of current leading heavy launch systems for an equivalent low earth orbit. Benefiting from scaling factors, this result could improve. The full model used to produce this result could not be properly included in this introductory article, and following publications will consolidate the basis presented.

The concept parallels traditional hybrid propulsion, sharing many advantages like relative simplicity, safety, throttling capability, and thermochemical performance equivalent to common liquid propulsion (LOX/RP-1). Naturally, it also shares challenges, particularly towards combustion, including solid regression and combustion efficiency. Solutions to most of these challenges were brought by recent scientific and industrial efforts, allowing to reach suitable performance for commercial applications.

The second axis of this technology, namely propellants insertion into the chamber, is addressed with a novel architecture with geometrical assets but which may not be as efficient as competing technologies like turbopumps. Further work is needed to model friction of sliding parts accurately and reduce mass to attain an optimal design. Additions featuring a thermodynamical cycle are considered to build a more efficient and scalable system than the electric-fed early version. Clear technical challenges are identified and were discussed in this article.

The third axis is about mechanical aspects of the combustible structure. The thermoplastic structure takes the form of a cylindrical tube, with its geometry determined by the mixture ratio of the engine. The thickness of approximately 15% of the structure radius for a LOX/PE

launcher. This value brings high levels of structural rigidity, especially in the cryogenic environment which tends to increase dramatically the elasticity modulus of polymers. Low temperatures also bring several constraints on the cooling process, and defects may also be able to create cracks that would endanger the brittle material. An interesting opportunity is found in polyethylene nuances, exhibiting good performance in every aspects mentioned.

Looking ahead, as technical challenges are overcome with the experimental projects following this introduction, the potential for excellent performance at a reduced cost becomes clear. Hybrid autophage propulsion presents a compelling opportunity to establish a new branch of launchers propulsion, combining established branches to ensure an easier, cleaner access to space.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the corresponding team at CNES (Centre National d'Études Spatiales) for their ongoing technical and financial support, allowing the development of this article and the coming first firing tests part of the Ambre project.

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